

Biblical Principles on Land Ownership towards Socio-economic and Wealth Distribution in Yorubaland

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Abstract

Land is a sacred inheritance entrusted by God to humanity for equitable use, stewardship, and the flourishing of all mankind. Within the biblical tradition, especially the Old Testament wealth distribution and land ownership are regulated through divine principles designed to promote justice, restore dignity, and protect the vulnerable. This study examined these biblical teachings, particularly the laws of Jubilee, gleaning, and tithing, and evaluates their relevance in addressing contemporary socioeconomic injustices in Yoruba land. The study adopted biblical-theological and contextual analytical method to investigate how scriptural ethics

intersect with the challenges of land exclusion, inequality, and legal dualities in Nigeria. The findings **emphasize** that land is not a commodity for personal enrichment but a communal trust requiring equitable and just stewardship, as evidenced in the biblical texts examined particularly the land laws and jubilee traditions (e.g., Lev 25; **Matthew 19:16–24**) which constitute the primary data for this study. The study therefore recommended that churches and civil societies should collaborate to apply these enduring principles, advocating for equity, transparency, and sustainable land governance in contemporary society.

Keywords: Land, Wealth Distribution, Justice, Stewardship, Socio-economic Inequality.

Introduction

Wealth and land ownership are central to both economic stability and societal equity. In many societies, including those in contemporary Nigeria, land signifies more than mere property. It is a source of identity, power, and generational legacy (Oladapo, 2019). The imbalance in land ownership, often stemming from historical, legal, and political systems, which continues to perpetuate poverty and marginalization among vulnerable populations.

The Bible, particularly in the Old Testament, offers strong principles concerning wealth distribution and the fair use of land. These principles are not only theological in nature but also serve as practical moral guides designed to uphold justice, compassion, and communal responsibility (Wright, 2003). Concepts such as the Jubilee year, gleaning rights, and tithing were established to discourage the excessive accumulation of wealth and to safeguard the poor from systemic exploitation (Baker, 2009). Prophets in the scripture frequently spoke out against economic oppression and called for righteousness in social dealings (Brueggemann, 1997).

However, disparities in land distribution have fueled economic inequality, resulting in widespread socio-economic injustices that systematically marginalize vulnerable populations and restrict equitable access to resources and opportunities.

This study examines how biblical teachings on wealth and land ownership can offer meaningful insights into addressing modern-day socio-economic inequality, with particular attention to the situation in Yorubaland. By analysing scriptural ideals alongside the region's current realities, the study aims to present biblically inspired responses to land related injustices and promote a society marked by fairness, dignity, and shared responsibility.

Statement of the Problem

Land is a sacred resource entrusted to mankind by God for stewardship, inheritance and equitable distribution. Land in Yorubaland is governed by customary tenure systems, wherein families or communities hold land collectively and transfer usage rights through inheritance. However, disparities in land distribution have fueled economic inequality, resulting in widespread socio-economic injustices that systematically marginalize vulnerable populations and restrict equitable access to resources and opportunities. As a result, many communities in Yorubaland face the commodification of land, where urban expansion, industrial development, and political interests

Yorubaland, known for its rich historical heritage and diverse ethnic population, is equally affected by this trend (Adebayo & Iweala, 2021). Christian teachings emphasize justice, stewardship, and love for one's neighbor, yet unequal land ownership in the region contradicts these principles by concentrating land and wealth in the hands of a few. This imbalance has contributed to persistent poverty and hardship among families who rely on land for sustenance and economic survival. Furthermore, the neglect of biblical values such as fairness, compassion, and care for the poor has exacerbated social exclusion, particularly affecting widows, orphans, and low-income households. As a result, land-

related injustices not only deepen economic inequality but also undermine the moral responsibility of the biblical principles to promote equity, stewardship, dignity, and social justice.

Theology of Land Ownership, and Stewardship

In the Biblical scripture, land is far more than a physical possession or a commodity to be traded. It holds spiritual, communal, and theological significance, deeply woven into the identity of God's people. The land was viewed not merely as property, but as a divine trust a sacred gift from God meant to sustain life, facilitate worship, and promote justice. Throughout Scripture, this understanding forms the basis for Israel's approach to land ownership and human responsibility.

The idea that God is the true owner of the land is clearly stated in Leviticus 25:23: "The land shall not be sold permanently, for the land is mine; you are but strangers and sojourners with me." This verse sets the foundation for a theology that places God at the centre of all economic and social systems. The people of Israel were not ultimate proprietors but stewards who held the land temporarily and were expected to use it responsibly. Ownership, in this sense, was relational and conditional, tied to obedience to God's covenant.

The distribution of land to the twelve tribes during the conquest of Canaan (Joshua 13–21) was conducted according to divine instruction, reinforcing the notion that land is an inheritance, not a commodity. Each clan was given a portion to maintain livelihood and stability, but laws such as the Year of Jubilee (Leviticus 25:8–55) ensured that ancestral land could not be permanently lost due to economic hardship. The goal was to maintain social balance and familial continuity, preventing the emergence of a permanent underclass. As Habel (1995) observes, biblical land laws reflect a theological commitment to inclusion, restoration, and the sacredness of place. Moreover, the prophets repeatedly criticised those who sought to expand their estates at the expense of others. Isaiah denounced those who "join house to house and add field to field" until no land is left for others (Isaiah 5:8). This reveals that unjust accumulation of land was not only a social issue but a theological violation an affront to God's intention for justice and equity in the community.

The concept of stewardship is equally central to biblical land theology. To be a steward is to act on behalf of another in this case, God. The call to care for the land involves more than cultivation; it includes preserving its fruitfulness, honouring the rights of others, and ensuring that future generations can benefit from its bounty. The Sabbath laws, which required the land to rest every seventh year (Leviticus 25:2–7), embody this principle. Such regulations acknowledge

the land's intrinsic value and remind humanity that their control over it has limits.

Old Testament Economic Laws

The Old Testament teaches, land is not an economic asset but a sacred trust bestowed by God upon His people. Leviticus 25:23 declare that “The land shall not be sold forever: for the land is mine; for ye are strangers and sojourners with me” (Holy Bible, RSV). This declaration underscores the principle of divine ownership, positioning God as the sovereign landlord, while humans are temporary tenants and stewards (Micheal & Shogunle, 2025, p. 82). The economic regulations outlined in the Old Testament were intended to foster justice, prevent the exploitation of the poor, and ensure communal well-being. Among the most notable of these laws are the principles of Jubilee, gleaning, and tithing, all of which shows God's concern for equitable wealth distribution and social responsibility. These laws reflect a theological vision in which wealth and land are not merely private possessions but divine trusts to be managed with righteousness and generosity.

The Jubilee law, as detailed in Leviticus 25:8–55, mandated that every fiftieth year, land that had been sold was to be returned to its original family owners. This act prevented the permanent loss of ancestral land and aimed to curtail generational poverty. Wright (2004) asserts that this law is a divine mechanism to reset economic inequalities and restore balance within the Israelite community. It served as a socio-economic safeguard to ensure that no family was permanently disenfranchised due to misfortune or debt (Brueggemann, 2014).

The law of gleaning, described in Leviticus 19:9–10 and Deuteronomy 24:19–22, instructed landowners not to harvest every corner of their fields but to leave portions for the poor, widows, orphans, and foreigners. This system allowed the marginalized to access food with dignity, without begging or complete dependence. Gleaning reinforced the communal ethic of care and reminded Israel that their land and produce ultimately belonged to God (Block, 1999). A vivid example of this principle is found in Ruth 2, where Boaz's adherence to the gleaning laws allows Ruth and Naomi to survive and be reintegrated into society. This story illustrates how Old Testament economic ethics were not only legislative but also life-transforming in practice.

The practice of tithing, outlined in Numbers 18:21–24, Deuteronomy 14:22–29, and Malachi 3:10, involved dedicating one-tenth of one's agricultural produce or income to support the Levites, the poor and religious functions. Tithes were not only religious offerings but also a system of redistribution that provides for

those who had no inheritance or land. Wenham (2003) emphasises that tithing was intended as an act of worship and a tool for social justice, bridging the gap between the rich and the poor within the covenant community. Tithing affirms that material resources are entrusted by God and must be used to sustain both spiritual service and communal welfare.

These economic laws reflect a divine intention for fairness, compassion, and accountability in human relationships. They also serve as enduring moral principles for addressing modern challenges related to poverty, inequality, and the ethical use of resources. Biblical principles such as the Jubilee, gleaning, and tithing offer societies a pathway toward economic systems rooted in equity, dignity, and collective responsibility.

Prophetic Denunciations of Economic Oppression

The Old Testament prophets played a critical role in confronting economic injustices within ancient Israel and Judah. Their messages consistently denounced the misuse of wealth, exploitation of the poor, and corruption among the elites. Far from being merely spiritual voices, the prophets served as social critics, calling leaders and the people to return to the covenant principles of equity and righteousness. Economic oppression for the prophets, was not only a moral failure but a direct violation of God's will for His covenant community (Habel, 1995). These prophetic messages prioritise justice over greed.

Amos, often recognised as the prophet of social justice, issued some of the strongest rebukes against economic exploitation. In Amos 5:11–12, he condemns the wealthy who “trample on the poor and exact grain taxes from them,” exposing how legal and economic systems were manipulated to enrich a few at the expense of many (RSV, 1984). He further declares that religious rituals are meaningless when injustice prevails: “I hate, I despise your festivals... But let justice roll on like a river, righteousness like a never-failing stream” (Amos 5:21, 24). Amos's message reveals that genuine worship must be inseparable from economic and social ethics, a principle that challenges contemporary societies to align spiritual practices with justice (Wright, 2003). Isaiah speaks against the elite who join “house to house and field to field” until no land is left for others, thereby depriving families of their ancestral inheritance (Isaiah 5:8). This condemnation resonates with the Mosaic emphasis on land as a divine gift that must not be monopolised, as articulated in Leviticus 25:23 (Wenham, 1994). Isaiah's prophetic vision links land accumulation with moral decay, warning that greed will lead to national judgement. His critique underscores the covenant obligation to maintain

equitable access to resources, offering significant guidance for addressing modern disparities in land ownership.

Micah also addresses systemic injustice, particularly among rulers and religious leaders who exploit their positions. In Micah 2:1–2, he laments those who “devise iniquity and work evil upon their beds... they covet fields and seize them” (RSV, 1984). Micah connects economic oppression with idolatry and corruption, forewarning divine punishment for such violations. His message, strongly focus on the covenant call to protect the vulnerable, he highlights the necessity of justice in the courts and marketplace, a principle that remains relevant for contemporary governance (Fretheim, 1995).

The prophets’ repeated call for justice reflects God’s unwavering concern for the poor, vulnerable and the demand for accountability from those in power. This theological ethic provides a timeless principle for confronting systemic inequities, urging societies to uphold the rights of the disadvantaged (Brueggemann, 2001). The prophets’ vision challenges modern communities to address economic oppression through policies that prioritise fairness and transparency.

Ethical Teachings on Wealth and Poverty

The New Testament particularly the ministry Jesus, affirmed the dignity of the poor and warned against the corrupting influence of wealth, and urged His followers to embrace lives marked by compassion and communal responsibility. Jesus’ teachings reflect a deep continuity with the Old Testament prophetic tradition, yet they also call for a radical transformation of social and personal priorities, embedded in the vision of God’s kingdom (Habel, 1995). This ethic offers profound insights into the moral use of resources, challenging societies to uphold the vulnerable and foster equity.

In the Sermon on the Mount, Jesus proclaims a blessing on “the poor in spirit,” stating that “theirs is the kingdom of heaven” (Matthew 5:3, NRSV). Luke’s Gospel speaks more directly to material poverty: “Blessed are you who are poor, for yours is the kingdom of God... But woe to you who are rich, for you have received your consolation” (Luke 6:20, 24). These words do not idealise poverty but highlight God’s concern for the lowly and His desire for justice in economic relations, echoing the Old Testament’s call to protect the marginalised (Wright, 2003). Jesus’ teachings serve as a warning against placing undue trust in material possessions, urging a reorientation towards divine values.

Jesus consistently challenged the pursuit and retention of wealth as potential barriers to true discipleship. In His encounter with the rich young man (Matthew 19:16–24), Jesus invited him to sell his possessions and give to the

poor. The man walks away sorrowful, Jesus remarks that it is difficult for the wealthy to enter the kingdom of God, comparing it to a camel passing through the eye of a needle. (Wenham, 1994) emphasises the spiritual danger of wealth when it becomes a source of security or pride rather than a means for serving others. It underscores the call to prioritise God’s kingdom over material gain. In Luke 16:19–31, the parable of the rich man and Lazarus offers a stark image of economic inequality and divine justice. The rich man’s failure to show compassion toward Lazarus, a poor man suffering outside his gate, leads to his ultimate separation from God. This parable serves as a solemn reminder that indifference to human suffering has serious moral and eternal consequences, reinforcing the Old Testament’s prophetic denunciations of economic oppression (Fretheim, 1995). Jesus’ narrative challenges believers to act with compassion, ensuring that wealth is used to alleviate suffering rather than perpetuate inequality.

Jesus promoted a life of generosity and simplicity, urging His listeners to “be on guard against all kinds of greed,” noting that “one’s life does not consist in the abundance of possessions” (Luke 12:15, NRSV). Instead of storing earthly wealth, He taught that people should seek treasures that endure in heaven (Matthew 6:19–21). The early Christian community, inspired by Jesus’ teachings, embodied these values through communal sharing and support for the needy. As recorded in Acts 2:44–45, believers sold their possessions and distributed the proceeds to ensure that no one among them lacked daily necessities. This practice reflected an economy grounded in love, mutual care, and the belief that all material goods ultimately belong to God, aligning with the Old Testament’s vision of wealth as a divine trust (Wright, 2003). Such communal living offers a model for modern communities seeking to address economic disparities through collective responsibility.

Socio-economic Injustice in Land Ownership in Yorubaland

Land ownership in Yorubaland, southwestern Nigeria, remains a highly sensitive and complex issue shaped by historical experiences, legal pluralism, and deeply rooted socio-cultural values. In Yoruba society, land is not merely an economic asset but a symbol of identity, ancestry, and continuity across generations. However, contemporary patterns of land acquisition and distribution increasingly reflect inequality, exclusion, and conflict. These socio-economic injustices expose systemic failures such as weak governance, legal ambiguities, and the erosion of communal responsibility, underscoring the urgent need for more equitable and ethically grounded land management practices (Habel, 1995).

Traditionally, land tenure in Yorubaland operates under customary systems in which land is collectively owned by families or communities and access is transferred through inheritance. These indigenous practices recognise the ancestral and spiritual significance of land, viewing it as a sacred trust entrusted to the living on behalf of past and future generations (Ògúnleye, 2018). However, this customary arrangement has been significantly undermined by the Land Use Act of 1978, which vested ultimate control of land in the hands of state governors. The imposition of statutory authority over communal land has weakened traditional governance structures, created legal uncertainty, and concentrated decision-making power within political institutions, often to the detriment of local communities (Wright, 2003). This tension between customary tenure and statutory control constitutes a central problem in land governance in Yorubaland.

As a result, land in Yorubaland has been commercialized, particularly in rapidly urban areas such as Ibadan, Akure, Abeokuta, and Lagos peripheries. Urban expansion, commercial development, and political interests have led to the displacement of indigenous landholding families and rural communities. Those without formal land titles or political influence especially small-scale farmers and the urban poor are frequently dispossessed without adequate compensation. Land speculation and elite accumulation of property have widened socio-economic inequalities, reinforcing poverty and insecurity among rural dwellers. Women experience compounded marginalisation, as patriarchal customs and formal legal systems often deny them inheritance and ownership rights, despite their significant contributions to household and agricultural labour (Ògúnleye, 2018). These realities deepen social injustice and contradict Christian ethical principles of fairness, stewardship, and care for the vulnerable. Land-related conflicts have consequently become pervasive across rural and peri-urban Yorubaland. Disputes involving families, community leaders, land speculators, and government agencies frequently arise from unclear land records, overlapping claims, boundary disputes, and land-grabbing practices linked to commercialisation. Such conflicts often escalate into violence, forced displacement, and long-standing social divisions. The complexity, cost, and inaccessibility of formal legal processes further marginalise the poor, leaving many victims of land injustice without effective means of redress (Fretheim, 1995). This exclusion erodes communal harmony that traditionally characterised Yoruba land tenure and stands in tension with biblical ethics that emphasise justice, peace, and the protection of the poor and dispossessed.

Biblical Response to Modern Wealth Disparities

The Bible offers a timeless and enduring principles to confront modern wealth disparities, grounded in God's character and Scripture's moral vision. These principles promote fairness, generosity, and protection of the vulnerable, providing ethical guidance for just societies (Habel, 1995). They remain relevant for addressing economic inequalities in Yorubaland.

The Old Testament sets clear standards for economic justice. Laws such as the Jubilee (Leviticus 25:8-55), gleaning (Leviticus 19:9-10), and tithing (Deuteronomy 14:28-29) mandate resource redistribution to uphold the dignity of the needy, recognising that hardship often stems from uncontrollable circumstances (Wenham, 1994). Prophets like Amos and Isaiah condemn oppression and wealth hoarding (Amos 5:11-12; Isaiah 10:1-2), urging equitable systems (Wright, 2003).

Jesus intensifies these concerns, teaching that wealth should serve others, not be idolised. His parables of the rich fool (Luke 12:16-21) and the rich man and Lazarus (Luke 16:19-31) warn against ignoring the poor, while His call to the rich young man (Matthew 19:21) demands radical generosity (Fretheim, 1995). These teachings challenge believers to prioritise compassion over accumulation. The early Church embodies these values through shared resources (Acts 2:44-45; 4:32-35). Paul's call for generosity, rooted in Christ's self-giving (2 Corinthians 8:9), marks economic compassion as central to discipleship (Brueggemann, 2001). This model of mutual aid offers profound insights for addressing wealth disparities today.

In Yorubaland, where land and economic inequalities persist, these biblical principles provide a moral foundation for reform. The Church and policymakers can advocate for equitable land access, fair wages, and ethical governance, aligning with Scripture's call to justice (Ògúnleye, 2018).

Conclusion

The challenges surrounding wealth distribution and land ownership in Yorubaland raise urgent concerns about justice, fairness, and the dignity of all individuals. The biblical tradition offers a consistent and compelling vision that prioritises the protection of the vulnerable and the equitable sharing of resources. From the Old Testament instructions on Jubilee, gleaning, and tithing, to the strong prophetic warnings against exploitation, and the communal economic practices of the early Church, Scripture affirms a model of society grounded in compassion, stewardship, and mutual responsibility.

The concept of land as a sacred trust stands in stark contrast to contemporary patterns of land exclusion, hoarding, and unjust acquisition. Addressing these

issues requires a deliberate return to values that place community well-being above individual gain. Embedding these principles into public policy and community development can guide the transformation of land governance and resource distribution across the state.

As Yorubaland continues to develop, the application of biblical principles offers a path toward social equity and sustainable development. The Church, alongside civil institutions, has a unique responsibility to promote these values through advocacy, education, and ethical leadership. By embracing these enduring truths, communities can move closer to a just and inclusive future where prosperity is shared, and every person has the opportunity to flourish.

Recommendations

In light of the findings of this study, it is recommended that land governance in Yorubaland be reformed through the integration of customary tenure systems with statutory law. Such reform would honour indigenous traditions while ensuring legal clarity and protection for vulnerable populations. There is also an urgent need to promote equitable access to land, particularly for women, the poor, and rural dwellers who are often excluded from formal ownership due to socio-cultural and legal constraints. Churches should be empowered to lead advocacy efforts, drawing from biblical teachings on stewardship and justice to challenge unjust systems and educate their congregations. In addition, legal and ethical literacy programmes should be introduced at the community level to equip citizens with the knowledge and tools to defend their land rights. Inspired by biblical models of redistribution, churches and local governments should support initiatives that provide resources to those in need, such as cooperative farming, food security schemes, and affordable land access programmes. Conflict resolution mechanisms involving traditional, religious, and legal institutions should also be strengthened to manage disputes peacefully and fairly. Sustainable stewardship of land must be encouraged, ensuring that its use today does not compromise the well-being of future generations.

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